

FUEL EFFECT ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH EVOLUTION OF CARBON FIBRES UNDER DIRECT FLAME ATTACK

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Abstract

PAN-based carbon fibres have been subjected to simultaneous tensile load and open flame attack using a hybrid tow-based approach. Their oxidation behaviour has been determined through TGA/DSC, whereas SEM was used to evaluate the morphology of burnt fibres.

The effect of a methane-based non-premixed turbulent flame on the tow tensile strength has been assessed by varying the applied load and time of fire exposure. Residual UTS evolves with respect to time of exposure.

Motivation – CFRP & Fire

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) are flammable. Typically found in primary and secondary aircraft structures [1], some of these need to act as firewalls where appropriate protection is needed [2].

Under fire attack, CFRP tensile strength mainly depends on the fibre integrity once the matrix has been decomposed. Hence the need to understand the effect of fire on them. Carbon fibre oxidation and gasification is driven by two major competing reactions [3]:

Method – Fire & Tensile Load

Teijin Carbon Fiber HTS45 12K Tow
 ↓
 Constant Tensile Load (% of virgin UTS) + 1100 °C (116 kW/m²) Flame*
 ↓
 Residual UTS (no flame): 100 mm/min until failure

*Non-premixed turbulent diluted:
 Fuel: CH₄ (45%) + CO₂ (55%)
 Oxidizer: O₂ (45%) + CO₂ (55%)

Test rig

Results

1 **TGA/DSC:** Single step weight loss behavior. Oxidation onset temperature above 500 °C. Exothermicity is linked to the heating rate.

TGA (a & b) and DSC (c) of HTS45 fibres.

4 **Post-fire Tensile Strength:** Under flame attack and 10% load (of virgin tow's UTS), an approximately linear decrease can be observed on the post-fire UTS with respect to time. A 20% load yielded similar average strength values with higher scatter. Considering a fixed test duration (120 s), different constant loads (up to 50%) do not have a significant impact on the residual UTS.

Residual UTS of fibre tows burnt at different intervals.

2 **Load & Fire (visual assessment):** Loaded carbon fibre tows get heterogeneously oxidized. The first fibres to fail are those on the tow's periphery. Progressive failure takes place inwards.

Fire & load test sequence: fibre tow in tension prior fire attack (a), start of fire test (b), partial tow failure (c) and fibre tow still under tensile load after fire attack before total failure (d).

3 **SEM:** Heterogeneous fibre diameter reduction within the carbon fibre tow along with localized pitting and channeling due to catalytic reactions (related to impurities originated at processing).

SEM of fibres: virgin (a) and exposed to flame for 120 s (b).

Residual UTS of burnt fibre tows (120 s) at different load levels.

Future Work

- Study the influence of flame chemistry, i.e. liquid and different gaseous fuels.
- Tests to be extended to CFRP laminates.

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Conclusions

- Carbon fibres subjected to severely oxidative conditions and load show decrease of UTS with increase of fire exposure.
- Surface defects along with fiber diameter reduction correlate with lower residual UTS.
- Large scatter of burnt fibre tows' post-fire UTS at higher constant load during fire exposure.
- Intra-tow fibre arrangement may translate into protection amongst fibers from oxidative species.

References

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